

Determining the effects of selected cutting parameters on Circularity and Cylindricity in turning operations for steel 4140 using Taguchi methods

Asif Khan¹

Department of Mechanical Engineering, HITEC University, Islamabad, Pakistan
Email: asifkhanghauri5@gmail.com

Qaiser Saghir

Department of Mechanical Engineering, HITEC University, Islamabad, Pakistan
Email: qaisergi104@gmail.com

Ali Raza

Department of Mechanical Engineering, HITEC University, Islamabad, Pakistan
Email: engnr.aliraja@gmail.com

Abstract: In the field of manufacturing, a manufacturer focuses to design manufacture and deliver such products that meet customers' requirements, the dimensional tolerances are focused, but it cannot be denied that geometrical tolerances also have same importance as dimensional tolerances have. Because when it is necessary to control more precisely the form or profile of some feature of a component because of the component specific functions that the part has to perform. For a reciprocating part it must be completely round and cylindrical similarly for rotating parts concentricity, cylindricity and for power transmitting shafts circularity, concentricity, straightness and cylindricity is necessary. After achieving all the dimensional and geometrical tolerances, it can be said that we are going towards repeatability and interchangeability. Steel 4140 have been used in this work due to its wide range of uses. The steel lies in the steel of "high tensile strength steels." L16 and L9 orthogonal array has been used for these experiments, one experiment as conformation test. All these parameters are related to round cylindrical mechanical components machined over turning machines depending on a number of factors including input power, cutting tool, tool materials, coolant type, cutting speed, feed rate, depth of cut, material removal rate and surface form etc. The parameters have been studied for different ratios between diameter and length. Design of experiments is a unique procedure used when the number of variables is more than one. This is a multivariable testing procedure which varies the factors concurrently due to the independence of each factor from other. Here only three variables are taken as the cutting speed, feed rate and cut depth as the process variables. Taguchi's algorithm of design of experiments is best to investigate the optimum cutting parameters of the expressed geometrical properties. The features studied are circularity and Cylindricity.

Keywords: Circularity, Cylindricity, Design of experiments, Taguchi, signals to noise ratio, turning operations, Taguchi methods, steel 4140, high tensile strength steels, cutting speed, feed rate, depth of cut, material removal rate, etc.

¹ Corresponding author

Introduction and Literature Review:

Turning operation is the most common mode for metal removing and particularly for the finishing of machined parts in the manufacturing industries. Optimization practices application in turning operation is necessary for growing quality of product and to sustain effectiveness in the manufacturing industries. In current situation, the supreme significant thing which is measured in manufacturing industries is the worth of a product. The worth of a product can be augmented by either enhancing the quality of products or sinking the price, environmental, and societal impacts. Geometrical features are the most critical measures in improving quality of products, performance of the system developed and service time of the mechanical products and it is a good factor to evaluate the sustainability of the machined products (Melesse et al., 2019; Hascalik and Cavdas, 2008; Nalbant et al., 2007; Asiltürk and Akkus, 2016; Asiltürk et al., 2016). Turning attributes to a major channel of components of being manufactured goods. Turning is an external surface machining, with rotating work piece, with a point cutting tool and parallel feed to the work piece cutting the required material from its surface (Groover, n.d.; Tokyo, 1990; Krishnaiah and Shahabudeen, 2012). Taguchi's method can be applied for optimization of the process parameters to produce high quality products that can encounter the goal of product sustainability (Kalpakjian and Schmid, 2003; Chaudhari et al., 2010). HSS Mirand S-400 with minimum quantity lubrication in turning for mild steel as working material gives best results of surface roughness and tool wear (Mustafa and Ali, 2011). The influence of DNMG150608-2C Kx20 inserts on Al 2017 as working material enhances the Surface Roughness, Work piece Cylindricity error and Vibration phenomenon. Vibration is very important in generation of surface Roughness and dimensional error in metal cutting. By minimizing vibration the process performance can be enhanced and product quality also can be improved (Hrishikesh et al., 2015). In the geometric control perpendicularity, circularity and Cylindricity were concentrated and these are controlled within the tolerances of Circularity = 0.005, Cylindricity = 0.007 and perpendicularity = 0.006 with different references (Tadvi et al., 2011; Harish et al., 2013). During machining of MS 1010 as working material and High-speed steel as cutting tool material for the results of surface roughness and dimensional tolerance, cutting speed has an impact of 59.9% (Sunil, 2015). In hard turning and performing analyzing for surface Roughness, H11 tool steel as working material and Sandvik Koromant CBN and inserts are CNGA120412, CNGA 120408, and CNGA 120404 as cutting tools feed rate and Nose Radius is significantly affecting on Ra while speed has insignificant effect on Ra (Steven, n.d.).

Design of experiments (DOEs):

Design of experiments is an old concept invented by Ronald A. Fisher in 1920s. The method of experimental design was used in an agricultural background, and later on this method was used in military and industry in 1940s successfully. DOEs is a structural way of conducting and organized way of analyzing controlled tests to assess those factors which are affecting output variables. DOEs identifies those particular setting levels of the couples of factors at which every run in the experiments to be conducted. This is a multivariable testing procedure which varies the factors simultaneously due to the independence of each factor from other. DOEs is a sequence of tests where focused changes are completed in the input variables of a process and their effects on output variables are checked (Bagchi, 2014; Ross, n.d.; Mukherjee, 2014; Brian et al., 2014; Steven, n.d.).

Smaller-is-best:-

SN= -10 Log (variance + mean).

Material specification:

Chromium steel:-The material that has been used is chromium steel whose related standards are given below. Hardness of the material used is 30HRC. Specified chemical composition recommended internationally shown in table 1 and that composition of tested sample in table 2 respectively.

Table 1 Specified Chemical Composition Recommended Internationally

C	Cr	Si	Mn
0.36~0.44	0.75~1.2	0.1~0.4	0.65~1.10
Mo	S	P	
0.15~0.35	~0.04	~0.05	

Table 2 Composition of Tested Sample

C	Cr	Si	Mn	Mo	S	P
0.42	1.04	0.23	0.75	0.18	0.006	0.02

Experimental work and Inspection:²

As explained in the earlier sections there are three parameters taken as independent input variables for experiments and two parameters as dependent output variables. After conduction of each experiment measurements have been taken as shown in the corresponding tables. On the basis of literature analysis, pre-experimentation work, unsuccessful experimentation work, material consumption, time consumption and cast of all factors said above levels of input parameters are finalized as mentioned below (Mukherjee, 2014; Brian, 2014). For this series of experiments diameter to length ratio has been taken 0.5 taking diameter 20mm and length is 40mm and the ranges of cutting conditions are as given in Table 1A. Table 1B is L16 orthogonal array shows the different levels of parameters and their variations in all levels. Here we considered the dia to length ratio $\varnothing/L= 0.5$

Table 1 A Parameters and their Levels

Parameters		Levels			
RPM	A	1600	1840	2010	2150
Cutting speed(m/min)		100	115	126	135
Feed rate (mm/rev)	B	0.08	0.10	0.12	0.14
Depth of cut (mm)	C	0.47	0.52	0.54	0.50

² First series of experiments

Table 1 B Different Levels of Parameters and Their Variations

Cutting speed (m/min)	Feed (mm/rev)	Doc (mm)
100	0.08	0.47
115	0.10	0.47
126	0.12	0.47
135	0.14	0.47
100	0.14	0.50
115	0.12	0.50
126	0.10	0.50
135	0.08	0.50
100	0.10	0.52
115	0.08	0.52
126	0.14	0.52
135	0.12	0.52
100	0.12	0.54
115	0.14	0.54
126	0.08	0.54

Operational run order:

Table 1C shows the sequence in which we will perform our experiments. The sequence of operations is set according to increasing order for depth of cut to make easy the setting of material removal in a proper way for the same size of diameter of all parts.

Table 1C Sequence of Experiments

RPM	Cutting speed (m/min)	Feed (mm/rev)	Doc (mm)
1600	100	0.08	0.47
1600	100	0.10	0.52
1600	100	0.12	0.54
1600	100	0.14	0.50
1840	115	0.08	0.52
1840	115	0.10	0.47
1840	115	0.12	0.50
1840	115	0.14	0.54
2010	126	0.08	0.54
2010	126	0.10	0.50
2010	126	0.12	0.47
2010	126	0.14	0.52
2150	135	0.08	0.50
2150	135	0.10	0.54
2150	135	0.12	0.52
2150	135	0.14	0.47

Inspection Reports:

The following table 1D is total inspection report for the said two parameters. All the readings are taken two times each for the purpose to minimize human error chances. All the valves are in millimeters. In this table T1 and T2 shows the number readings taken.

Table 1 D Total Inspection Report

S No	Circularity		Cylindricity	
	T1	T2	T1	T2

1	0.015	0.015	0.017	0.017
2	0.012	0.012	0.016	0.016
3	0.013	0.013	0.014	0.014
4	0.015	0.016	0.016	0.016
5	0.012	0.012	0.012	0.014
6	0.016	0.016	0.015	0.016
7	0.014	0.014	0.016	0.016
8	0.010	0.010	0.016	0.016
9	0.008	0.007	0.009	0.009
10	0.003	0.003	0.004	0.004
11	0.005	0.005	0.008	0.007
12	0.004	0.005	0.006	0.006
13	0.018	0.018	0.02	0.019
14	0.012	0.012	0.007	0.007
15	0.011	0.011	0.01	0.01
16	0.016	0.016	0.017	0.017

Table 1F Individual Readings of Circularity

Cutting speed	Feed Rate	Depth of cut	Circularity T1	Circularity T2	SNRA	PSNRA
100	0.08	0.47	0.015	0.015	36.4782	34.5447
100	0.10	0.52	0.012	0.012	38.4164	39.4179
100	0.12	0.54	0.013	0.013	37.7211	37.5461
100	0.14	0.50	0.015	0.016	36.1888	37.2959
115	0.08	0.52	0.012	0.012	38.4164	37.3348
115	0.10	0.47	0.016	0.016	35.9176	37.9312
115	0.12	0.50	0.014	0.014	37.0774	38.1982
115	0.14	0.54	0.010	0.010	40.0000	37.9472
126	0.08	0.54	0.008	0.007	42.4795	44.8744
126	0.10	0.50	0.003	0.003	50.4576	47.6095
126	0.12	0.47	0.005	0.005	46.0206	45.7343
126	0.14	0.52	0.004	0.005	46.8825	47.6220
135	0.08	0.50	0.018	0.018	34.8945	35.5148
135	0.10	0.54	0.012	0.012	38.4164	38.2493
135	0.12	0.52	0.011	0.011	39.1721	38.5127
135	0.14	0.47	0.016	0.016	35.9176	36.1238

Taguchi's Analysis for circularity and S/N ratio for circularity:

The table 1F consists of individual readings of circularity against each level and each parameter, their S/N ratios, and predicted S/N ratios calculated as response table for circularity. Table 1F provides data for response of each variable parameter, the values of delta and their contribution status or rank that is known as response table.

Response table for S/N ratio for Circularity:

In response tables the S/N ratios are given against each parameter as given in table 1F. According Taguchi's procedures these S/N ratios are added for each level of each parameter and then their average is calculated. And a new table for these values is generated where all the values are given. Table 1G is given below where columns consist of parameters and rows numbers of levels the lower most two columns show the delta values and ranks of each parameter. Rank means contribution of the parameters individually.

Table 1 G The Values of Delta and their Contribution Status or Rank.

Level	cutting speed	Feed Rate	depth of cut
1	37.20	38.07	38.58
2	37.85	40.80	39.65
3	46.46	40.00	40.72
4	37.10	39.75	39.65
Delta	9.36	2.73	2.14

Mean Effects Plots for SN Ratios for Circularity:

Plots in Fig 1 show the individual effects of all parameters over circularity. The plots are drawn circularity vs speed, circularity vs feed rate and circularity vs depth of cut respectively. Here from the Fig 1 given below it is clear that 126 m/min, 0.10 mm/rev and 0.52 mm are the required couple of cutting conditions that give the optimum values of circularity.

Interaction plot for Circularity:

The interaction plot in fig 2 shows the interactions of S/N ratio for circularity against all the cutting parameters. As minimization of the output parameters is required so here smaller is better is selected to maximize mathematical expression for S/N ratio for circularity. In the Fig 2 all the possible Taguchi's combinations are shown and the respective average S/N ratios, it is clear from all phases of given graph that 126 m/min, 0.10 mm/rev and 0.52 mm is the required couple cutting conditions that gives the optimum values of circularity. In the figure green, red and red line shows the cutting speed, feed rate and depth of cut respectively. These lines show the optimality of the conditions in the form of average S/N ratios for circularity.

Figure 1 & 2: Individual Effects of all Parameters over Circularity & Interactions

Taguchi’s analysis for Circularity and S/N ratio for Circularity:

The table 2 A consists of individual readings of Circularity against each level and each parameter their S/N ratios and predicted S/N ratios calculated as response table for Circularity.

Table 2 A individual readings of Circularity and S/N ratios

Cutting Speed	Feed Rate	Depth of Cut	Circularity T1	Circularity T2	SNRA	PSNRA
100	0.08	0.47	0.017	0.017	35.3910	33.1757
100	0.10	0.52	0.016	0.016	35.9176	39.0669
100	0.12	0.54	0.014	0.014	37.0774	36.8842
100	0.14	0.50	0.016	0.016	35.9176	35.1769
115	0.08	0.52	0.012	0.014	37.6955	35.6795
115	0.10	0.47	0.015	0.016	36.1888	37.2709
115	0.12	0.50	0.016	0.016	35.9176	36.4837
115	0.14	0.54	0.016	0.016	35.9176	36.2853
126	0.08	0.54	0.009	0.009	40.9151	42.9368
126	0.10	0.50	0.004	0.004	47.9588	45.9236
126	0.12	0.47	0.008	0.007	42.4795	42.8665
126	0.14	0.52	0.006	0.006	44.4370	44.0635
135	0.08	0.50	0.02	0.019	34.1965	36.4061
135	0.10	0.54	0.007	0.007	43.0980	40.9019
135	0.12	0.52	0.01	0.01	40.0000	39.2401
135	0.14	0.47	0.017	0.017	35.3910	36.1374

Response Table for S/N ratio for Cylindricity:

In response tables the S/N ratios are given against each parameter as given in table 2A given above. According Taguchi's procedures these S/N ratios are added for each level of each parameter and then their average is calculated. And a new table for these values is generated where all the values are given. Table 2B is given below where columns consist of parameters and rows numbers of levels the lower most two columns show the delta values and ranks of each parameter. Rank means contribution of the parameters individually.

Table 2 B Response of Variable Parameters, the Values of Delta and Contribution Rank

Level	Cutting Speed	Feed Rate	Depth of Cut
1	36.08	37.05	37.36
2	36.43	4079	38.50
3	43.95	38.87	39.51
4	38.17	37.92	39.25
Delta	7.87	3.74	2.15
Rank	1	2	3

Mean affects plots for SN ratios for cylindricity:

These lines show the optimality of the conditions in the form of average S/N ratios for Cylindricity in Fig 3.

Fig 3 & 4: Ratios for Cylindricity & Possible Taguchi's Combinations

Interaction plot for Cylindricity:

The interaction plots in fig 4 shows the interactions of S/N ratio for cylindricity against all the cutting parameters. As minimization of the output parameters is required so here smaller is better is selected to maximize mathematical expression for S/N ratio for Cylindricity. In the Fig 4

all the possible Taguchi's combinations are shown and the respective average S/N ratios, it is clear from all phases of given graph that 126 m/min, 0.10 mm/rev and 0.52 mm is the required couple cutting conditions that gives the optimum values of Cylindricity however for best surface finishing 0.50 mm depth of cut gives best results in the above cases. Here in the figure green, red and red line shows the cutting speed, feed rate and depth of cut respectively. These lines show the optimality of the conditions in the form of average S/N ratios for Cylindricity.

Experimental work and Inspection:³

For this series of experiments diameter 15 mm and length is 30 mm so that to maintain dia to length ratio as 0.5 and the ranges of cutting conditions are as given in Table 3A. Table 3B is L9 orthogonal array shows the different levels of parameters and their variations in all levels in Table 3C. Remaining procedures of "Inspection Reports" as in Table 3B1, Taguchi's analysis and S/N ratio for circularity and cylindricity" "Response tables for S/N ratio" "Mean Effects Plots for SN Ratios" Interaction plot for Circularity and cylindricity are adopted as like in first series of experiments. Response tables the S/N ratios are given against each parameter as given in "Table 3C". Table 3D is Response of Variable Parameters, the Values of Delta and Contribution Rank for circularity, Table 3E and Table 3F show response of each variable parameter, the values of delta and their contribution status or rank for cylindricity respectively. "Taguchi analysis." Fig 5, Fig 6, Fig 7 and Fig 8 are mean affect plots and interaction plots for circularity and cylindricity respectively.

Table 3 A Parameters and Levels

Parameters		Levels		
RPM	A	2150	2210	2360
Cutting speed(m/min)		101	104	111
Feed rate (mm/rev)	B	0.08	0.10	0.12
Depth of cut (mm)	C	0.47	0.50	0.52

Table 3 B different levels of parameters and their variations

S No	Cutting speed (m/min)	Feed (mm/rev)	Doc (mm)
1	101	0.08	0.47
6	104	0.12	0.47
8	111	0.10	0.47
2	101	0.12	0.50
4	104	0.10	0.50
9	111	0.08	0.50
3	101	0.10	0.52
5	104	0.08	0.52
7	111	0.12	0.52

³ Second series of experiments

Table 3 B 1 Total Inspection Report

S No	Circularity		Cylindricity	
	T 1	T 2	T 1	T 2
1	0.005	0.005	0.007	0.007
2	0.006	0.006	0.008	0.008
3	0.003	0.003	0.005	0.005
4	0.004	0.004	0.006	0.006
5	0.003	0.003	0.004	0.004
6	0.007	0.007	0.007	0.007
7	0.005	0.005	0.006	0.005
8	0.004	0.004	0.007	0.006
9	0.007	0.007	0.008	0.007

Table 3 C Response of each variable parameter for circularity

Cutting speed	Feed Rate	Depth of cut	Circularity T1	Circularity T2	SNRA	PSNRA
101	0.08	0.47	0.005	0.005	46.0206	46.1071
101	0.10	0.52	0.006	0.006	44.4370	46.5303
101	0.12	0.50	0.003	0.003	50.4576	48.2777
104	0.08	0.52	0.004	0.004	47.9588	45.7790
104	0.10	0.50	0.003	0.003	50.4576	50.5441
104	0.12	0.47	0.007	0.007	43.0980	45.1914
111	0.08	0.50	0.005	0.005	46.0206	48.1140
111	0.10	0.47	0.004	0.004	47.9588	45.7790
111	0.12	0.52	0.007	0.007	43.0980	43.1845

Table 3 D Response of Variable Parameters, the Values of Delta and Contribution Rank

Level	Cutting Speed	Feed Rate	Depth of Cut
1	46.97	46.67	45.69
2	47.17	47.62	48.98
3	45.69	45.55	45.16
Delta	1.48	2.07	3.81
Rank	3	2	1

Table 3 E Individual Readings

Cutting Speed	Feed Rate	Depth of Cut	Cylindricity T1	Cylindricity T2	SNRA	PSNRA
101	0.08	0.47	0.007	0.007	43.0980	42.7974
101	0.10	0.52	0.008	0.008	41.9382	42.7519
101	0.12	0.50	0.005	0.005	46.0206	45.5075
104	0.08	0.52	0.006	0.006	44.4370	43.9239
104	0.10	0.50	0.004	0.004	47.9588	47.6582
104	0.12	0.47	0.007	0.007	43.0980	43.9118
111	0.08	0.50	0.006	0.005	45.1570	45.9707
111	0.10	0.47	0.007	0.006	43.7161	43.2030
111	0.12	0.52	0.008	0.007	42.4795	42.1789

Table 3F values of delta and their contribution status or rank

Level	cutting speed	Feed Rate	depth of cut
1	43.69	44.23	43.30
2	45.16	44.54	46.38
3	43.78	43.87	42.95
Delta	1.48	0.67	3.43
Rank	2	3	1

Fig: 5 Mean Affect Plots and Interaction Plots for Circularity and Cylindricity

Fig 6: Mean Affect Plots and Interaction Plots for Circularity and Cylindricity

Fig 7: Mean Affect Plots and Interaction Plots for Circularity and Cylindricity

Fig 8: Mean Affect Plots and Interaction Plots for Circularity and Cylindricity

Conclusion and Future recommendation:

Here the Optimized conditions for Circularity and Cylindricity for both series of experiments are concluded and the results of verification experiments on the basis of those conditions are given:

Optimized conditions for Circularity			Optimized conditions for Cylindricity		
126/3	0.1/2	0.50/2	126/3	0.1/2	0.50/2
Optimized conditions for Circularity			Optimized conditions for Cylindricity		
104/2	0.1/2	0.50/2	104/2	0.1/2	0.50/2
Verification experiments and measurements 1 st Run					
Feature	Couple of Parameter	Result	S/N Ratio	Predicted S/N Ratio	Error %
Circularity	126, 0.1, 0.50	0.005	46.0206	47.60953	3.33741
Cylindricity	126, 0.1, 0.50	0.006	44.43697	45.92365	3.23727
Verification experiments and measurements 2 nd Run					
Circularity	104, 0.1, 0.50	0.004	47.9588	50.54406	5.11486
Cylindricity	104, 0.1, 0.50	0.005	46.0206	47.65816	3.43605

Conclusions:

In the current investigation some of the most important machining parameters are proposed for machining process. Taguchi’s method has been used to investigate the main influencing parameters affecting the geometrical features such as surface finishing, circularity and

Cylindricity. Through this series of experiments of machining the summarized conclusions are given below:

A surface finishing of 0.15μ maximum achievable taken as standard reference for selection of all Parameters. Through Taguchi's analysis for diameter to length ratio 0.50 for first series of experiments it has been observed that third level of cutting speed and second level of feed rate and depth of cut is very significant. This couple of parameters is 126 mm/min cutting speed, 0.10 mm/rev feed rate and 0.50 mm depth of cut. For second series of experiments the couple of parameters are 104 mm/min cutting speed, 0.1 mm/rev feed rate and 0.50 mm depth of cut.

Future recommendations:

For the same cutting conditions material removal rate and surface finishing effects can be studied. Only one type of material has been selected for the experimental work and materials like tool steel can be used as all these geometrical features are very important in manufacturing of thread plug gauges, thread ring gauges specially in case of concentricity gauges, Because the use of gauges increases production rates. The quality of work can be more enhance by changing the other machining conditions like type of coolant, type of cutting tools, type of cutting tool radius, type of tool material and by changing the hardness of working material. The procedures can be applied for any type of steel to find out the optimum cutting conditions to reduce machining time and to increase production.

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